

NOS donor Schiff base and their nickel(II) complexes : Synthesis, characterization, electrochemical and antimicrobial studies

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Abstract : A series of nickel(II) complexes [Ni(L)(L¹)] (1), [Ni(L)(PMDT)] (2) and [Ni(L)(Dien)] (3) have been synthesized with newly synthesized Schiff base derived from 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and 2-aminothiophenol, L = (4-bromo-2-[(2-sulfanylphenyl)imino]methyl}phenol), PMDT = *N,N,N',N',N''*-pentamethyldiethylenetriamine, Dien = diethylenetriamine, L¹ = *N*-[(1-pyridin-2-ylmethylidene)benzohydrazide]. The elemental analysis of the complexes were confined to the stoichiometry of the type [M(L)(A)]. In view of analytical, spectroscopic and magnetic studies, it has been concluded that the nickel(II) complexes possess octahedral (1-3) geometry. The redox behavior of the complexes, investigated with the aid of cyclic voltammetry, indicated the two-electron transfer process. The antimicrobial activities of Schiff base and the complexes against *E. coli* were studied by the minimum inhibitory concentration method revealed that the Schiff bases and some of their metal complexes possess antibacterial activity.

Keywords : Nickel(II) complex, electrochemical, antimicrobial, magnetic studies.

Introduction

A variety of nitrogen and sulfur donor ligands and their complexes have been investigated involving both five and six membered heterocyclic thiol ring¹. Most of such studies have largely been concentrated on various pyridine-derived ligands^{2,3}. Schiff base ligands particularly molecules possessing nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur donor sites are important in the development of coordination chemistry as well as in the biomimetic chemistry of a number of metal ions, particularly the transition metals⁴. They show interesting properties, e.g. their ability to reversibly bind oxygen, catalytic activity in hydrogenation of olefins, photochromic properties, and complexing ability towards toxic metals. The interest of studying Schiff bases containing ONS donors arose from their significant antifungal, antibacterial, and anticancer activities. In addition, the presence of both a hard and a soft donor group in one ligand increases the coordination ability towards hard as well as soft acidic metals. The N, O and S atom play a key role in the coordination of metals at the active sites of numerous metallo-biomolecules. The chemistry of (4-bromo-2-[(2-sulfanylphenyl)imino]methyl}phenol) has attracted widespread attention due to diverse biological activities.

The metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from

sulfur containing compounds have also proven to be important pharmaceutical agents^{5,6}. Schiff bases are fairly good biological agents and exhibit excellent importance in medicine and biochemistry. Nickel(II) complexes containing sulfur donors have received considerable attention due to the identification of a sulfur rich coordination environment in biological nickel centers, such as the active sites of certain urase, methyl-*S*-coenzyme-*M*-methyl reductase and hydrogenase^{5,7}. The synthesis of low molecular weight nickel(II) complexes mimicking Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) activity has been challenging for bioinorganic chemists and recently some complexes with high catalytic activity have been reported⁸⁻¹⁰. Nickel-containing superoxide dismutase (NiSOD) has been isolated from several *Streptomyces* species^{11,12}. The enzymatic activity of NiSOD¹³ is as high as that of Cu-ZnSOD at about 10⁹ M⁻¹ s⁻¹ per metal center. Continuing our work¹⁴ on the biological activity of Schiff base compounds with *S,N*-heterocyclic adducts we report the synthesis of new complexes [Ni(L)(L')]⁽¹⁾, [Ni(L)(PMDT)]⁽²⁾ and [Ni(L)(Dien)]⁽³⁾ with Schiff base of 2-aminothiophenol. This is due to their antibiotic, anti-inflammatory¹⁵, antifungal¹⁶, anticonvulsant, local anesthetic, fungicidal, bactericidal, herbicidal, antiulcer, antineoplastic¹⁷ and anti-hypertensive¹⁸ properties.

Results and discussion

All the sulphur containing nickel(II) complexes are hygroscopic in nature. These are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMSO. The elemental analysis show that the nickel(II) complexes have nonstoichiometric ratio. Several attempts were made to develop the single crystal of the complexes but failed due to insolubility of the complexes in common organic solvents. All the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. All complexes were prepared by the following sequential routes (Scheme 1).

The IR spectra of the complexes also give expected band shapes and positions (Table 1). A high intensity band at 1610 cm^{-1} for the Schiff bases is attributed to the (C=N) vibration^{19,22} and is found to be slightly shifted to lower frequencies by *ca.* $4\text{--}15\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating the involvement of N-atom of the azomethine group in coordination of the metal^{23–25}. The coordination of the azomethine nitrogen is further evidenced by the presence of a new band in the range $400\text{--}489\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to (Ni–N) for these complexes²⁶. The shifting of the (N–N) frequency also supported the coordination

Scheme 1. Synthesis of complexes (1, 2 and 3).

Table 1. The important infrared frequencies (in cm^{-1}) of Schiff bases and their metal complexes

Complex	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{N}_{\text{py}})$	$\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{S})$
H_2L	–	1589	756	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
L^1	1269	1590	–	–	3274	–	–	–	–	–
1	1273	1582	759	1025	3350	–	670	486	430	340
2	1274	1581	753	–	–	–	–	489	429	350
3	1270	1587	757	–	3360	3411, 3242	–	488	428	348

through the azomethine nitrogen in the complexes. The appearance of band in the 428 cm^{-1} is due to the (Ni–O) stretching in the spectra of complexes²⁷. Medium intensity bands in the $1581\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region are regarded as combination of C=N and C=C stretching vibration of the aromatic ring. The bands in the range $1317\text{--}1320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to (C–S) frequency. The IR spectra of complexes contain strong band in the region $753\text{--}759\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which has been assigned to $\nu(\text{C–S})$ indicating coordination via thiolate sulfur. The negative shift of (CS) in the complexes has already been indicated by Campbell²⁸. The Ni–S vibration appears in the region $340\text{--}360\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the coordination through sulfur atom. Coordination via the thiophenolato sulfur is confirmed by the presence of new band in the range $320\text{--}350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to (Ni–S) for these complexes. The absorption band at 670 cm^{-1} is indicative of pyridine coordination³⁰ in complex **1**.

The electronic spectral assignments of the complexes are given in the Table 2. All complexes shows a ring $\pi\cdots\pi^*$ band at $\sim 34000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and an $n\cdots\pi^*$ band involv-

Table 2. Electronic spectral assignments of the Ni^{II} complexes

Complex	$\pi\cdots\pi^*$ (cm^{-1})	$n\cdots\pi^*$ (cm^{-1})	LMCT (cm^{-1})	$d\text{--}d$ (cm^{-1})
1	34100	30010	26010	17241
2	34050	29800	25850	17060
3	33900	29850	25000	17361

ing transitions within the thiophenol moiety, mainly C=N and C–S groups³¹ at $\sim 30000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands are slightly shifted upon complexation. The shift of the $\pi\cdots\pi^*$ bands to a longer wave length region is the result of the C–S bond being weakened and the conjugation system

being enhanced on complexation^{32,33}. The $n\cdots\pi^*$ bands in the complexes show a blue shift due to donation of the lone pair of electrons to the metal and hence the coordination of the azomethine with a reduction of intensity. Complexes **1**, **2** and **3** shows ligand to metal charge transfer bands as 26010 for **1**, 25850 for **2** and 25000 cm^{-1} for **3** respectively. Their positions are dependent on the steric requirements of the substituent. Each complex has a $d\text{--}d$ combination band that appears as a shoulder on the intra ligand and charge-transfer bands. In complexes LMCT maxima of the phenolate complexes show line broadening with a tail running into the visible part of the spectrum. This may result from a phenolate to Ni^{II} LMCT band being superimposed on the low energy side of the $\text{S}\rightarrow\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ LMCT.

The molar conductivity of the complexes were measured in DMSO solution ($3 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$). The molar conductivity data ($48\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ for **1**, $42\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ for **2** and $49\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ for **3**) indicated that all complexes were non-electrolytes³⁴, suggesting that the two ligands are covalently bonded with the metal ions.

Nickel(II) ion has the electronic configuration $3d^8$ and should exhibit a magnetic moment higher than expected for two unpaired electrons in octahedral (2.8–3.2 B.M.)^{35,36} and tetrahedral (3.4–4.2 B.M.) complexes where as its square planar complexes would be diamagnetic. The room temperature effective magnetic moments μ_{eff} of all the three complexes **1**, **2** and **3** found to be 2.89, 2.79 and 2.83 B.M. respectively consistent with the octahedral geometry.

The redox properties of 1 mM solution of the complexes were examined in DMSO containing 0.1 M NaClO₄ as supporting electrolyte at a glassy carbon working electrode. The results are presented in Table 3. From the

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data for 1 mM solution of the Ni^{II} complexes in DMSO containing 0.1 M NaClO₄ as supporting electrolytes

Complex	Scan rate	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μA)	E_{pa} (mV)	I_{pa} (μA)	ΔE_{p} (mV)	E^{O} (mV)	$I_{\text{pa}}/I_{\text{pc}}$ (μA)
1	100	-726	3.24	606	0.855	1332	-60	3.7
	200	-786	3.91	668	1.04	1454	-59	3.7
	300	-800	4.16	685	1.26	1485	-58	3.3
2	100	-685	3.12	595	0.798	1280	-45	3.9
	200	-740	3.76	680	0.988	1420	-30	3.8
	300	-761	3.98	691	1.18	1452	-35	3.4
3	100	-705	2.89	591	0.712	1296	57	3.8
	200	-715	3.49	656	0.926	1400	30	3.8
	300	-724	3.58	660	1.06	1420	32	3.4

$$\Delta E_{\text{p}} = E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}}; E^{\text{O}} = (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})/2.$$

Fig. 1 it is clear that the voltammetric behavior of complex is characterized by one fairly broad peak both in the cathodic wave and in the anodic wave. The cathodic po-

sentative graph showing IC_{50} value for complex 1 is given in Fig. 2 and data of the SOD activity assay along with kinetic catalytic constants of 1-3 complexes^{42,43} are pre-

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of complex 1 in DMSO (0.1 M NaClO₄ as supporting electrolyte, scan rate : 100 mV/s).

tential (E_{pc}) shifted from -0.726 V to -0.800 V/SCE, whereas the anodic potential (E_{pa}) shifted from 0.606 to 0.685 V going to faster scan rates. The separation between peaks ($\Delta E_p = E_{pc} - E_{pa}$) varies from 1332 to 1485 mV. This behavior is characteristic of irreversible process. An irreversible reduction peak in the region -0.72 to -0.80 V is obtained for complexes on a cathodic scan. This peak has been assigned to reduction of the ligand³⁷. Similarly anodic scan of all the complexes show an irreversible oxidation in the region 0.60 to 0.68 V, so this oxidation is definitely a ligand based oxidation. Constancy of E^0 shows that both peaks are complementary to each other in all cases. It seems that the complex molecule experiences any structural change that accompany the reduction process, probably due to the rigidity of the NOS ligating system³⁸.

These complexes exhibit significant catalytic activity toward the dismutation of superoxide anions. Superoxide was generated from alkaline DMSO and SOD activity was evaluated by the NBT assay³⁹⁻⁴¹ following the reduction of NBT to MF⁺ kinetically at 560 nm. The repre-

Fig. 2. SOD activity of complex $[Ni(H_2L)(L^1)]$ (1).

sented in Table 4. Complex 1 shows highest SOD activity ($IC_{50} = 42 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) whereas complexes 2 and 3 showed SOD activity $IC_{50} = 58$ and $65 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively.

The antimicrobial activity of the ligand and their nickel(II) metal complexes were assayed against *E. coli* by Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)⁴⁴ method

Table 4. IC₅₀ values and kinetic constant of 1-3

Complex	IC ₅₀ (μmol)	$k_{McCF} (M^{-1} s^{-1}) \times 10^4$
1	42	2.26
2	58	1.63
3	65	1.46

k_{McCF} were calculated by $K = k_{NBT} \times [NBT]/IC_{50}$, k_{NBT} (pH 7.8) = $5.94 \times 10^4 M^{-1} s^{-1}$.

with three different concentration of 15, 20 and 25 μg/L. The activity was also assayed for the pure solvent DMSO. The zone of inhibition in millimeter for the control, ligand and their Ni^{II} complexes are presented in Table 5 and Figs. 3-5. The representative graph showing antibacterial activity is given in Fig. 6. From the data of metal complexes it is clear that the metal chelates exhibit higher

Table 5. Antibacterial results of Schiff base and their metal complexes

Complex	Concn. (μg L ⁻¹)	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)
		<i>E. coli</i>
H ₂ L	0.003	No clear zone
1	0.001	1.0
	0.002	1.5
	0.003	2.0
2	0.001	No clear zone
	0.002	No clear zone
	0.003	0.8
3	0.001	1.5
	0.002	2.5
	0.003	3

DMSO (Control) No clear zone

Key to interpretation for 100 μg L⁻¹ : less than 12 mm - inactive; 12-16 mm - moderately active; above 16 mm - highly active.

Fig. 3. A representative photograph of the size of inhibition diameter of control against *E. coli* bacteria.

Fig. 4. A representative photograph of the size of inhibition diameter of ligand H₂L against *E. coli* bacteria.

Fig. 5. A representative photograph of the size of inhibition diameter of complex [Ni(H₂L)(L¹)] (1) against *E. coli* bacteria.

Fig. 6. Antibacterial activity of complex [Ni(H₂L)(L¹)] (1).

antimicrobial activity than that of the free ligand molecule.

The biological activities of synthesized Schiff bases and their complexes were studied for their antimicrobial activities by agar diffusion method. The antibacterial activities were done at 15, 20 and 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ concentration in DMSO solvent using bacteria *E. coli* strains by the minimum inhibitory concentration method. The bacteria was incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. Activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone.

Experimental

Nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate was purchased from Across Organics, India. All other chemical used were of synthetic grade and used without further purification.

Synthesis of H_2L :

The ligand (H_2L) was synthesized according to the method reported¹³ in the literature. 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde (2.011 g, 10 mmol) and 2-aminothiophenol (1.25 g, 10 mmol), each dissolved in 10 ml ethanol were mixed with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for 1 h. Solution of this reaction mixture was refluxed continuously for 4 h after adding 1–2 drops of acetic acid. On cooling the solution brown crystals of (4-bromo-2-[(2-sulfanyphenyl)imino]methyl)phenol) were separated, which were filtered and washed with methanol and diethylether. Dried brown crystals were stored in CaCl_2 desiccators. Yield 2.94 g (95%) (Found : C, 50.01; H, 3.10; N, 4.21. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrNOS}$: C, 50.66; H, 3.27; N, 4.54%); FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 308.19; Found : 309.9.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of ligand H_2L .

Synthesis of ligand L^1 :

The Schiff base of heteroaromatic aldehyde was prepared by adopting the reported procedure of Klayman¹³. The Schiff base was synthesized by condensation of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde and benzoylhydrazine. A solution of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (1.071 g, 10 mmol) and benzoylhydrazine (1.361 g, 10 mmol) was stirred continuously for 1 h. After 1 h stirring reaction mixture was refluxed for another 3 h after adding 1–2 drops of acetic acid. On cooling the solution at room temperature pale yellow crystals were separated which were filtered and washed with small amount of ethanol. The product was stored in CaCl_2 desiccator. Yield 2.06 g (85%) (Found : C, 69.02; H, 4.56; N, 18.45. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 69.25; H, 4.88; N, 18.64%).

Scheme 3. Synthesis of ligand L^1 .

Synthesis of complex $[\text{Ni}(L)(L^1)]$ (1) :

A MeOH solution (10 mL) of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.291 g, 1.0 mmol) was mixed in a solution (10 mL) of L (0.214 g, 1.0 mmol) and stirred for 1 h. After 1 h stirring a MeOH solution (10 mL) of L^1 (0.225 g, 1.0 mmol) was added. The resulting solution was continued to stir for 3 h. After the completion of the reaction, brown sticky complex was obtained. The resultant precipitated complex was filtered and collected. These were washed with MeOH and diethyl ether and dried in air at room temperature and stored in CaCl_2 desiccator. Yield 0.448 g (87%) (Found : C, 51.89; H, 3.21; N, 9.25. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrNiN}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (1) : C, 52.92; H, 3.25; N, 9.49%); FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 590.11; Found : 591.89.

Synthesis of complexes [Ni(L)(PMDT)] (2), [Ni(L)(Dien)] (3) :

To a stirred solution of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (0.291 g, 1.0 mmol) in MeOH (10 mL) and H₂L (0.214 g, 1 mmol), a MeOH solution (10 mL) of PMDT (0.20 g, 1.0 mmol) was added at room temperature. The resulting solution was continued to stir for another 30 min. After 2 h of stirring at room temperature the yellowish brown precipitate was obtained. The precipitated complex was filtered and was washed with methanol, dried in air and stored in CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield 0.655 g (82%) (Found : C, 50.89; H, 5.26; N, 10.10. Calcd. for C₂₂H₃₁BrNiN₄OS (2) : C, 49.10; H, 5.81; N, 10.41%); FAB Mass (*m/z*) Calcd. : 538.17; Found : 539.2. Complex 3 was synthesized in a similar way as 2, only the difference is that the Dien (0.95 g, 1 mmol) was added in place of PMDT. Slow evaporation of reaction mixture afforded the complex 3 as a dark brown precipitated complex. Yield 1.37 g (89%) (Found : C, 42.89; H, 4.68; N, 11.69. Calcd. for C₁₇H₂₁BrNiN₄OS (3) : C, 43.63; H, 4.52; N, 11.97%); FAB Mass (*m/z*) Calcd. : 468.03; Found : 471.38.

Elemental analyses of the complexes were performed on an Elementar Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 analyser. FAB Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA 6000 mass spectrometer/data system using xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. UV-Vis spectra were recorded at 25 °C on a Shimadzu UV-Visible recording spectrophotometer UV-160 in quartz cells. IR spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance using a mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units). Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a BAS-100 Epsilon electrochemical analyzer having an electrochemical cell with a three-electrode system. Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode, glassy carbon as working electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode. 0.1 M NaClO₄ was used as supporting electrolyte and DMSO as solvent. All measurements were carried out at 298 K under a nitrogen atmosphere. Molar conductivities of the freshly prepared 2×10^{-3} M of DMSO solutions were measured on a Systronics conductivity TDS meter 308.

Conclusion :

We have described the synthesis and characterization of three new nickel(II) complexes : [Ni(L)(L¹)] (1), [Ni(L)(PMDT)] (2) and [Ni(L)(Dien)] (3). Magnetic moment and spectroscopic data show the paramagnetic nature of the nickel(II) complexes. Structural analysis reveals that all complexes adopt distorted octahedral MN₆ environments, coordinated through nitrogen and oxygen atoms. Metal centered process are strongly influenced by the nature of sulfur bonding which dominate the redox behavior of these complexes.

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